

What is 'Protecting Victoria's Environment - Biodiversity 2037' and why is it important?

Biodiversity is a priority, as it underpins health, wellbeing, and security through ecological systems, flora, and fauna. Maintaining biodiversity is essential, yet human consumption exceeds Earth's regenerative capacity as within 2019, global demand uses 175% of resources the planet could reproduce, through fossil fuels (Raven & Wackernagel, 2020). This imbalance drastically altered environmental conditions, threatening species survival evidenced by Nunez *et al.* (2019) that identified an increase of 2 degrees celsius through CO₂, predicting a 14% decline within flora and fauna through higher temperatures. In response, policymakers, environmental organisations have prioritised biodiversity management to maintain taxonomic consistency across species. In Victoria, Environment Victoria (2017) introduced 'Protecting Victoria's Environment - Biodiversity 2037', a statewide policy aimed at reshaping societal perspectives to integrate environmental practices around biodiversity.

The Victorian Government's 'Protecting Victoria's Environment - Biodiversity 2037' manages biodiversity through three objectives: informing the public of biodiversity's significance, securing investment from stakeholders, and reviewing changes over time. This policy cycle is around 'Informing', 'Understanding', and 'Integrating' biodiversity practices to promote long-term sustainability.

While this policy fosters biodiversity conservation, the scientific evidence utilised requires closer scrutiny. Evidence-based/scientific knowledge plays a crucial role in policy formation, providing measurable indicators of procedural success through data, thereby reducing ambiguity and bias (Pfaff & Schmitt, 2023). The extent which scientific evidence is used for policymaking determines the validity of decisions made under 'Protecting Victoria's Environment - Biodiversity 2037', as government officials such as Lily D'Ambrosio must ensure policies are grounded in scientific research.

Assessing 'Protecting Victoria's Environment - Biodiversity 2037' integration of evidence

The policy 'Protecting Victoria's Environment - Biodiversity 2037', identifies a presence and lack of evidence justifying steps taken to sustain biodiversity. Page 33) exemplifies this where Victoria Parks findings describe that sustaining biodiversity, appreciating nature within parks generates 1.4 billion dollars a year while providing 14,000 jobs. These statistics prioritise biodiversity within parks through a trusted source in 'Victoria Parks' representative of the 'Adoption' step described in the APS200 project as it solidifies the importance of the policy through context (Australian Government, 2012). In contrast, a lack of evidence is present when justifying decisions within Page 17) within strategies provided like 'reintroducing apex predators'.

The lack of evidence comes from three factors: quantity, quality, and transparency with the previous case lacking quantity, as no evidence justified the 'Reintroduction of apex predators' as a strategy. Further examples show lacking evidence through minimal clarity regarding the "Forum" processes discussed on Page 39) as although suggestions were made that "Forums" promote ownership of biodiversity practices, the document doesn't discuss how these "Forums" meet 'Statewide targets'. Evidence is needed to justify specific strategies and detail how processes are integrated to achieve biodiversity goals through greater quantity, distribution of evidence.

The policy also lacks evidence justifying decisions, particularly on Page 24), which states that "People who spend time in nature... recognise its importance to their wellbeing" without explaining how. While evidence supports public integration in biodiversity management, the quality is insufficient as it doesn't detail methodologies utilised to establish statements provided, complicating the necessary approach.

Finally, the policy's statistics lack transparency, as seen within Page 5) that cites a \$46 million savings in infrastructure through flood protection, but the source, 'Parks Victoria,' doesn't acknowledge limitations/costs used to save infrastructure. Furthermore, the presence of potential bias within 'Parks Victoria' who benefits from higher biodiversity through tourism hasn't been acknowledged presenting potential issues regarding the evidence used as it may suggest an agenda. To improve quality and transparency, the policy cycle should provide specific evidence and use multiple sources to avoid bias within the creation of policies for the future.

Strategies to integrate scientific evidence into policy - making

To remedy the lack of evidence, transparency and integration can be employed regarding scientific evidence within the 'Protecting Victoria's Environment - Biodiversity 2037' policy cycle. Utilising a framework from the APS200 project ensures evidence is utilised to minimise ambiguity, uncertainty and bias during policy development.

The APS200 project by the Australian Government (2012), integrates scientific evidence into policy development by utilising a five-step approach in: anticipation (issue identification), formulation (policy development), consultation (contextual integration), adoption (funding and implementation), and evaluation (adjustments and improvements). The initiative ensures short and long term integration of scientific evidence within our decisions by establishing strategies for evidence-based policymaking which can be applied to the 'Protecting Victoria's Environment - Biodiversity 2037' policy as a lifelong practice.

The policy document lacks scientific evidence to support its processes and fails to outline methods for biodiversity protection. Within the APS200 project, this issue affects the 'Formulation' step, which relies on developing scientific evidence sources to assess effective conservation methods. The document presents ambiguous statements without justification, such as the implications of 'Reintroducing apex predators' or not clarifying methods used to determine how 'Spending time in nature improves wellbeing'. To enhance evidence integration within 'Formulation', a short-term approach would involve activities that synthesise, summarise, and communicate scientific knowledge to stakeholders.

Short term strategy: Synthesising scientific knowledge for policy audience

Integrating scientific knowledge into practice is challenging due to interpretation, uncertainty, and information overload, to enhance understanding, evidence should be synthesised through interrelated concepts (NAS, 2017). The DIKW (Data-Information-Knowledge-Wisdom) model by Nativi *et al.* (2019) offers a structured approach, categorising scientific data through 'Essential variables' and a four-step synthesis process to contextualise, sort and justify knowledge to ensure policy makers understand scientific knowledge integrated within policy development. Organising and correlating information through context makes scientific knowledge transparent and clear to foster trust between scientists, policy makers and the public to strengthen evidence-based policymaking (Intemann, 2023). Synthesising scientific knowledge provides a structured approach to biodiversity conservation policies by clarifying the 'What,' 'How,' and 'Why.' tied to knowledge allowing policymakers to grasp the impact of their decisions and identify necessary changes to effectively support biodiversity.

Although the DIKW model is effective, there lie problems when translating data, within interpretation that influences relevant or irrelevant data within policy making process resulting in shifts within policy approaches and trust if the actions are misguided (Rowley, 2007). An example of this is within Gonon *et al.*'s (2011) article that describes how policy makers extrapolated data regarding the DRD4 gene to medicalise ADHD. As a result, public attitudes emphasized genetic indifferences rather than addressing the issue, fostering unhealthy perspectives on the concern (Gonon, *et al.*, 2011). Misinterpretation regarding data guiding policy development creates exaggerated policies that don't resolve concurrent issues resulting in distrust and unhealthy practices between scientists, policymakers, and the public so although structured synthesis builds short-term trust within biodiversity policies, transparency remains essential to prevent skepticism.

Long term strategy: Sustaining interaction between scientists and policy makers

Another strategy to ensure long-term scientific evidence integration within 'Protecting Victoria's Environment - Biodiversity 2037', is through sustaining interactions between scientists and

policymakers. This can be facilitated through Knowledge Brokers, who act as intermediaries by presenting key statistics, evidence, and nuanced insights from literature, to highlight overlooked concerns for policymakers (Smits *et al.*, 2018). As Juhala *et al.* (2024) notes, Knowledge Brokers enhance networking by contextualising scientific information to address communication barriers, divergent perspectives, lack of trust, and difficulties processing complex information to ensure both parties develop effective approaches for sharing and using scientific evidence (Juhala *et al.*, 2024). Conceptualising change depends on linking ideas and exchanging data equitably, with both parties contributing to integrating scientific evidence through trust and transparency (Ward *et al.*, 2009). Establishing long-term collaboration between scientists and policymakers built upon transparency, enables Knowledge Brokers to select relevant data for the policy cycle, reinforcing scientific research into the decision-making processes.

While the relationships foster trust to incorporate scientific evidence, challenges arise when balancing equity within decision-making. Although including scientific data in policies is perceived as neutral, differences in intentions and perspectives lead to complications as both politicians and scientists may selectively use evidence to shape policy outcomes (Tieberghien & Decorte, 2013). Tieberghien & Decorte (2013) highlight this issue in drug policy development, where despite consulting scientists, politicians disregarded evidence to inform their decisions, prioritising the negative effects of cannabis over its medical applications to align with their agenda. While fostering trust and transparency between scientists and policymakers is crucial, there's a lack of regulation ensuring scientific advice is objective, leaving the process vulnerable to selective evidence use.

The conclusion from the 'Protecting Victoria's Environment - Biodiversity 2037' policy

In conclusion, while 'Protecting Victoria's Environment - Biodiversity 2037' safeguard's biodiversity by engaging with the public, its effectiveness is hindered by insufficient evidence integration, vague policy processes, and incoherent sequencing. Strengthening this policy requires rigorous scientific justification, ensuring decisions are supported by concrete data over broad assertions while analysing the policy problem (Formulation). Short-term improvements can be achieved through structured models like DIKW that make scientific knowledge accessible, while long-term success depends on fostering trust between scientists and policymakers via Knowledge Brokers. However, the risk of selective evidence use and personal agendas undermines the policy's credibility and impact. For 'Protecting Victoria's Environment - Biodiversity 2037' to remain actionable, it must prioritise transparency and evidence-driven decision-making to foster effective environmental conservation.

Reference List

Australian Government (2012) *APS200 project: The place of science in policy development in the Public Service*. Australian Government: Department of Industry, Innovation, Science, Research and Tertiary Education.

<https://webarchive.nla.gov.au/awa/20140212162547/http://www.innovation.gov.au/science/Pages/Library%20Card/APS200ScienceinPolicyReport.aspx>

Environment Victoria. (2017). *Protecting Victoria's Environment - Biodiversity 2037* (1). Victoria State Government.

https://www.environment.vic.gov.au/data/assets/pdf_file/0022/51259/Protecting-Victorias-Environment-Biodiversity-2037.pdf

Gonon, F., Bezar, E. Boraud, T. (2011). Misrepresentation of Neuroscience Data Might Give Rise to Misleading Conclusions in the Media: The Case of Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder. *PLoS ONE*, 6(1), 1 - 8. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0014618>

Intemann, K. (2023). Science communication and public trust in science. *Interdisciplinary Science Reviews*, 48(2), 350 - 365. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03080188.2022.2152244>

Juhala, S., Huotari, E., Kolehmainen, L., Silfverberg, O. & Korhonen-Kurki, K. (2024). Knowledge brokering at the environmental science-policy interface - examining structure and activity. *Environmental Science & Policy*, 153(1), 1 - 10. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2024.103672>

National Academies of Sciences, Engineering and Medicine; Division of Behavioral and Social Sciences and Education; Committee on the Science of Science (NAS) (2017). The Complexities of Communicating Science. *Communicating Science Effectively: A Research Agenda*. National Academic Press. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK425719/>

Nativi, S., Santoro, M., Giuliani, G. & Mazzetti, P. (2019). Towards a knowledge base to support global change policy goals. *International Journal of Digital Earth*, 13(2), 188 - 216.

<https://www.tandfonline.com/action/showCitFormats?doi=10.1080/17538947.2018.1559367>

- Nunez, S., Arets, E., Alkemade, R., Verwer, C. & Leemans, R. (2019). Assessing the impacts of climate change on biodiversity: is below 2°C enough? *Climate change*, 154(1), 351 - 365. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10584-019-02420-x>
- Raven, P. & Wackernagel, M. (2020). Maintaining biodiversity will define our long-term success. *Plant Diversity*, 42(4), 211 - 220. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pld.2020.06.002>
- Rowley, J. (2007). The wisdom hierarchy: representations of the DIKW hierarchy. *Journal of Information Science*, 33(2), 163 - 180. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0165551506070706>
- Smits, P., Denis, J - L., Preval, J., Lindquist, E. & Aguirre, M. (2018). Getting evidence to travel inside public systems: what organisational brokering capacities exist for evidence-based policy? *Health Research Policy and Systems*, 16(122), 1 - 6. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12961-018-0393-y>
- Tieberghien, J. Decorte, T. (2013). Understanding the science-policy nexus in Belgium: An analysis of the drug policy debate (1996 - 2003). *Drugs: Education, prevention and policy*, 20(3), 241 - 248. <https://doi.org/10.3109/09687637.2012.759904>
- Ward, V., House, A. & Harner, S. (2009). Knowledge Brokering: The missing link in the evidence to action chain? *Evidence & Policy*, 5(3), 267 - 279. <https://doi.org/10.1332/174426409X463811>